

1 **Impact of Studded Tire Use on Pavement Structures in Cold Climates**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 In cold regions, such as Alaska, using studded tires is common among the public when driving in
3 icy and snowy conditions. However, studded tires cause extensive wear to asphalt pavement,
4 reducing pavement life. This study utilized wear rate models and proposed a methodology to
5 quantify the pavement damage as a result of studded tires. The approach is applied in a case study
6 from a sample of Alaska statewide road segments. Parking lot surveys and household surveys were
7 employed to examine the extent of studded tire use in the state and alternative cost-effective
8 solutions for the Alaska roadway network. A pavement life cycle cost review was established
9 considering a number of variables to discover a realistic cost of roadway resurfacing and
10 rehabilitation. Wear rates due to studded tires and rut rates due to wheel loads were found for
11 different highway classes. Results show higher average wear rates due to studded passenger
12 vehicles on freeways (0.0116 in. per 100,000 studded vehicles) than the average rut rates due to
13 heavy wheel loads (0.0049 in. per 100,000 trucks) and lower average wear rates on arterial and
14 collector roads (0.0062 in. and 0.0045 in. per 100,000 studded vehicles, respectively). Finally,
15 estimates showed that studded tire use reduced asphalt surface life on the selected freeway sample
16 in the case study by about 7 years, which is about 47% loss in pavement life based on the initial
17 design life of 15 years.

18
19 **Keywords:** Wear rates, Pavement Rutting, Studded Tires, Pavement Life Cycle Cost Analysis

1 **INTRODUCTION**

2 In cold regions, studded tire use is considered a factor that contributes to pavement rutting
3 and damage. In Alaska, just like in other cold environments, pavement deterioration leads to
4 increased cost associated with pavement resurfacing (Abaza et al., 2017). The heavy wheel loads
5 of trucks cause noteworthy damage to highway pavement as well. The Alaska Department of
6 Transportation and Public Facilities (DOT&PF) is concerned about this issue and looking for
7 feasible solutions to mitigate the damage. Alaska is well known for its extreme temperatures. In
8 Interior Alaska, winter temperatures have been recorded as low as -40°F, and summer temperatures
9 have been recorded as high as 100°F. This extreme temperature range makes construction of
10 roadways and transport challenging. Due to its northern latitude, Alaska, in some locations,
11 experiences 24 hours of daylight in summer, and far less daylight in winter, adding further
12 challenges. Alaska’s immense size, coupled with high mountain ranges and huge glacier fields,
13 increases the cost of building roads, making it prohibitive in much of the state, particularly in
14 villages and towns in rural Alaska (AFHCP, 2018).

15
16 One common pavement defect caused by excessive use of studded tires is “rutting.” The
17 leading countries in studded tire use are Nordic countries, especially Finland and Sweden. Studded
18 tire use estimates range from 95% in Finland (Leppänen, 1997) to 49% in Alaska (Hicks et al.
19 1990). In Alaska, historical studded tire use was 73% in 1970 and decreased to 49% in 1990 (Hicks
20 et al. 1990). Then the percentage has remained about the same from 1990 to 2003 (Zubeck et al.,
21 2004). Sweden has mandated winter tire use and lately asserted use during winter months. A 1996
22 study in Oregon estimated the annual cost to repair damage caused to its highways by studded tires,
23 prior to lightweight stud regulations, at \$37 million (1994 USD) (Brunette and Lundy, 1996).
24 Another study in Oregon quantified the current use of studded tires, wear rates, and associated
25 costs. Several techniques were used to account for the extent of studded tire use, from parking lot
26 surveys to household surveys. That study showed a decline in studded tire use from 16% (1995)
27 to 4% (2013) for registered vehicles during winter months and calculated an asphalt pavement
28 wear rate of 0.0295 in. per 100,000 studded tire passes (Shippen et al., 2014). The present study
29 has conducted a comparable methodology and assessment of studded tire use on roads in Alaska
30 to quantify the net damage cost of pavement surfaces.

31
32 **Existing literature**

33 Studded tires contribute to rutting of roadways in Alaska and contribute partially to the wear of
34 marking stripes. In Alaska’s central and south coast regions, the lifespan of pavement subject to
35 studded tire wear is unspecified but is far shorter than the lifespan of pavement in the Lower 48.
36 Based on the past construction projects in Anchorage, pavement resurfacing life due to rutting
37 ranges from 7 to 9 years with an average of 8 years for freeways and higher for other road class
38 such as arterials and collectors (Arafat, 2018). Previous studies showed that studded tire use,
39 regardless of its other benefits, inflicts certain amounts of damage to road systems. Studded tires
40 contribute to the wear of HMA (hot-mix asphalt) and concrete pavement, eventually forming ruts
41 on the pavement surface. Thus, it can be noted that studded tire laws and regulations vary by state.
42 Some states allow unrestricted use of studded snow tires, while others set seasonal restrictions or
43 prohibit studded snow tires.

44
45 Studded tire wear is considered one of the major distresses affecting the roadways in Alaska,
46 especially on higher volume roads in the Central Region. The early rut monitoring programs that
47 were carried out by Alaska DOT&PF reported that the studded tire wear rate in winter was

1 significantly more than the rut caused by plastic deformation in summer as shown in Figure 1.

2
3
4 **Figure 1. Rut Depth Progression (Iskra, 2018).**

5
6 The scientific literature review showed that different pavement wear rates were published
7 earlier in other states like Alaska, Washington and Oregon. The Alaska DOT&PF estimated in 1996
8 wear rates of 0.102–0.148 in. per million passes (Barter 1996). Oregon DOT’s reported wear rates
9 of 0.34 in. per million passes (Angerinos et al., 1999). In addition, a technical brief from
10 Washington Department of Transportation reported total annual pavement damages of \$8 to \$10
11 million on the Oregon state highways, and \$16 million annual pavement damages from
12 Washington Department of Transportation (WSDOT, 2012).

13
14 Shippen et al., (2014) focused on quantifying the current use of studded tires and the wear
15 and cost caused by that use. The study reported a decline in studded tire use from about 16% of
16 registered vehicles in 1995 to about 4% in the 2013–2014 winter seasons. The wear rate of Portland
17 cement concrete (PCC) was about 0.0091 in. per 100,000 studded tire passes, while the wear rate
18 of asphalt pavement was about 0.0295 in. per 100,000 studded tire passes. A published technical
19 brief (WSDOT, 2012) discussed the total Washington statewide asphalt cost due to studded tires.
20 The rutting due to studs depends on the rate of wear and the number of vehicles with studded tires
21 being driven on the road. The report concluded that the studded tire usage rates vary from the west
22 side of Washington (estimated at about 9% of vehicles) to the east side of Washington (estimated
23 at 25% of vehicles).

24
25 Gray (1997) qualitatively supported the premise that there is no social or safety benefit
26 from studded tire use in Oregon. Quantitative cost analysis was limited to pavement rutting on the
27 state highway system that is sufficient to reduce the useful life cycle of the pavement. A range of
28 wear rates was estimated, reflecting the numerous factors that influence rutting susceptibility of
29 pavements. The mid-points of wear rates for asphalt and PCC were 0.0386 in. and 0.0093 in.,
30 respectively. Brunette and Lundy (1995) reported that studded tire wear shortens pavement life on
31 high-volume routes in Oregon. Asphalt pavements that experience average daily traffic (ADT)
32 volumes of 35,000 and 20% studded tire use were found to reach the threshold rut (3/4 in.) in 7
33 years. Portland cement concrete pavements that experience 120,000 ADT and 20% studded tire
34 use were found to develop the threshold rut depth of 19 mm in 8 years.

1 According to a study done in Sweden (Jacobson and Hornvall, 1999), wear was measured
2 through the SPS ratio (specific wear, grams of abraded material per vehicle with studded tires, and
3 kilometer). This measure has no constant for a certain pavement type, but an approximate estimate
4 of actual wear in specific conditions and during a specific period. The SPS average has decreased
5 from 30 during the late 1980s to 8 at the turn of the century. The most wear-resistant pavements
6 have SPS ratios of 2–4. In the winter season of 1994/95, wear was calculated to be 300,000 tons;
7 in the late 1990s, wear had diminished to around 110,000 tons. In Minnesota, the average terminal
8 wear rates for normal bituminous wearing courses ranged between 0.75 in. and 0.95 in. per million
9 studded tire passes (Preus, 1971). For conventional concrete pavements, the corresponding wear
10 rates ranged from 0.30 to 0.47 in. per million studded tire passes.

11 **METHODOLOGY**

12 To estimate the current percentage of studded tire use in Alaska, a parking lot survey and
13 an online household survey were conducted by the Department of Civil Engineering at the
14 University of Alaska Anchorage. A total of 1226 vehicles were surveyed in the parking lots
15 throughout the Anchorage area. More than 800 households, altogether owning 1531 vehicles,
16 responded to the household online survey. This followed by selecting sites for rut depth
17 measurements and traffic data from several samples including freeway, arterial and collector roads
18 as a case study. Data were collected from the Pavement Management and Statewide Planning
19 teams at the Alaska DOT&PF. Wear rate estimates from studded tire traffic and truck traffic were
20 calculated for each freeway sample. After establishing the theme from freeways and determining
21 the contribution of stud wear on pavement, a comparable methodology was applied for arterial and
22 collector roads. Pavement repaving/ resurfacing life cost was estimated from as-builts of 20 real
23 historical projects. Finally, the cost of total pavement damage from studded tire use was estimated.

24 **Data Collection**

25 The research method was carried out by collecting different types of data sets that include estimates
26 of studded-tire use, traffic volumes, traffic classification, roadway characteristics, and rut depth
27 measurements. These data collection procedures are explained in the following sub-sections;

28 *Percentage of studded tire use*

29 As previously mentioned, a parking survey was conducted from a sample of parking lots in
30 Anchorage area. The survey covered heavily used parking areas, mostly at shopping centers and
31 major generators. Seven sites were selected in Anchorage across different sections of the city to
32 gain a diversity of respondents. The sample population represented a variety of income levels and
33 educational levels. An additional site in Eagle River was considered to cover a broader geographic
34 region, though this was accomplished primarily through the online survey, which covered all
35 regions of Alaska. The selected sites include public institutions, commercial centers, private
36 institutions, and shopping centers.

37 The sample size used was determined using the following formula:

$$38 \quad n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{E^2} \quad (1)$$

39 Where:

40 n is the sample size, Z is a number based on the confidence level, p and q are the variance of the
41 population, and E is the maximum error of the estimation.

42 The confidence level is 95% (Z = 1.96) and the margin of error is 5%. The most conservative
43 variance estimates for both p and q are 0.5. The calculation of sample size yielded that a minimum
44

1 of 385 distinct vehicles were needed for the survey. The research team observed at least 75 vehicles
2 at each of the eight sites, nearly doubling the minimum required for the purposes of this survey.
3 The survey was conducted twice for each site to verify possible inconsistency of the data collection
4 between visits for the same site. General information of the parking site, including region within
5 the city, type of business, parking type, parking system, and payment method, etc. were recorded.
6 Then the following information was obtained about a minimum of 75 vehicles per site: vehicle
7 type, drive type, types of wheel (studded or non-studded), use of studs (front, rear, or both).
8

9 In addition to the parking lot survey, an online Qualtrics survey was programmed and sent
10 out to the public through different outlets. The survey was programmed not only to determine the
11 percentage of studded tire use, but also to capture the public point of view on using studded tires
12 or any other alternatives. Different questions were designed to test public awareness and the
13 public's experience with new technology in winter tires. The survey responses were received from
14 more than 800 households, owning 1531 vehicles altogether. These households represent a
15 balanced sample relative to population from all of Alaska's major cities including Anchorage, Palmer,
16 Wasilla, Fairbanks, Juneau, and Kenai.
17

18 *Traffic data and rut depth measurements*

19 Alaska traffic data and rut depth measurements were derived from a sample of freeways, arterials
20 and collector roads in the state. Statistically, a minimum sample size of three sites for each roadway
21 classification was considered for the significant wear rate analysis. These sites were selected based
22 on the available actual data before any resurfacing, maintenance, or rehabilitation projects done
23 by the Alaska DOT&PF. Data on annual average daily traffic (AADT) and Highway traffic data
24 were collected from permanent stations located on various highway segments. Other traffic
25 characteristics such as growth rates and average monthly daily traffic were taken from Alaska
26 DOT&PF Traffic Volume Reports, published annually on the department's website (DOT&PF,
27 2013 and Abaza et al., 2019). For each permanent counter location, data sets were tabulated and
28 classified by directional split to define the percentage of traffic moving in each direction, by lane
29 split to show the distribution of traffic among the right and left lanes, and by vehicle classification
30 to indicate the percentage of passenger vehicle and truck traffic. In addition, traffic growth rates
31 were used to estimate the total average daily traffic encountered over the total pavement
32 rehabilitation life for each roadway segment.
33

34 **Wear rates analysis**

35 It is hard to identify the pavement damage from studded tires caused in a specific year, as the life
36 of pavement spans many years and collected rut measurements are the cumulative fractions of
37 inches that develop over time. The pavement design life is 15 years for all classes of roadways in
38 urban Anchorage area based on Alaska flexible pavement design manual (McHattie, 2004). An
39 estimate was derived for cumulative studded tire wear. First, the total number of years was
40 calculated for each highway segment, from when the last resurfacing project occurred on that
41 segment until that segment's pavement reached the rut threshold or until the segment's next
42 resurfacing project date scheduled by Alaska DOT&PF. Then an estimate for the total number of
43 studded tire passes was calculated for each highway segment based on the following criteria;
44 Adjusted total traffic volume data using factors for the relative level of traffic during the studded
45 tire season, from September 15 until May 1 (regional differences apply here for projects outside
46 Alaska's central region); The percentage of traffic made up of total passenger vehicles and trucks;
47 The portion of vehicles in overall traffic volume using studded tires.

1 Rut is expressed as a function of cumulative studded tire passes over the road surface to
 2 identify the wear rate general model under the following assumptions. (a) The wear rate is constant
 3 because it stabilizes after 100,000 studded tire passes (Malik, 2000), and (b) It was assumed in the
 4 initial step of the calculation that all rutting in the left lane of a typical roadway is caused by
 5 studded tires resulting from passenger vehicles only. Then the rut rate is calculated based on actual
 6 percentage of trucks on each lane.

7
 8 After establishing the theme from freeways and determining the contribution of studs wear
 9 on the pavement, a comparable methodology was applied for the arterial and collector roads.
 10 Because many factors that affect wear rate were present, data were analyzed under the same
 11 conditions to eliminate the contribution of these factors. Variables such as speed, pavement design,
 12 and materials were constant for each highway segment. The only variables taken into consideration
 13 were traffic volumes and traffic classification on highway segments. The wear rate estimate is
 14 based on the assumption that the same type of metal studs, commonly used in the U.S. tire market,
 15 are used.

16
 17 Each data set in the rut measurements was combined with traffic data and current estimates
 18 of studded tire use. No information is available in the literature that shows methods to differentiate
 19 between rutting wear from studs and rutting wear from wheel loads. An assumption was made that
 20 trucks tend to travel predominantly in the right lane. A study done in Oregon (Malik, 2000) was
 21 able to resolve this challenge by summing the rut depth of each lane for every highway segment,
 22 then performing a regression of the combined depth against total directional studded tire traffic.

23
 24 According to Alaska traffic law, in the state's central region, 7.5 months is the time allowed
 25 for the public to use studded tires—from September 15 to May 1. The AADT in the total number
 26 of days during that period was multiplied by the percentage of traffic split between the right and
 27 left lanes to get the total number of vehicles on respective lane. In addition, studies of studded tire
 28 rutting have shown that pavement surfaces have a higher initial wear rate. Rut rates stabilize after
 29 100,000 studded tire passes (Malik, 2000). Therefore, wear rates were calculated per 100,000
 30 entering vehicles and trucks for each highway segment. Wear rates were expressed as a function
 31 of rut depth over traffic volume. The wear rate models were generated for each highway sample,
 32 as shown in equations below.

33 First, the wear rate in left lane by passenger vehicles are calculated considering all ruts
 34 coming from passenger vehicle only using Equation (2)

$$35 \quad WR_{PV_left} = \frac{Rut_{left}}{Traffic_{7.5month} \times Left_lane_{split} \times \%Studs} \quad (2)$$

36
 37 Where,

38 WR_{PV_left} = Wear rate due to passenger vehicle on the left lane (in/100,000 passes),

39 $Traffic_{7.5month}$ = Total number of traffic during winter season of the period considered,

40 Rut_{left} = Rut depth observed on the left lane (inches),

41 $Left_lane_{split}$ = Percentage of traffic moving on the left lane, and

42 $\%Studs$ = Percentage of passenger vehicles using studded tires

43
 44

1 Since the percentage of trucks are too low in left lane, the rut depth caused by actual number
2 of passenger vehicle are calculated using the Equation (3)

$$3 \quad Rut_{PV_left} = WR_{PV_left} \times Traffic_{7.5month} \times Left_lane_{split} \times \%Studs \times \%PV_{left} \quad (3)$$

4 Where, $\%PV_{left}$ = Percentage of passenger vehicles moving on the left lane

5
6 Then, the rut depth due to trucks in left lane is found by subtracting the rut depth due to
7 passenger vehicle from the total rut depth in the left lane using Equation 4. This remaining rut is
8 used to estimate the truck rut rate in the left lane which is considered equal to the rate in the right
9 lane for trucks as shown in Equation (5).

$$11 \quad Rut_{Truck_left} = Rut_{left} - Rut_{PV_left} \quad (4)$$

$$12 \quad WR_{Truck_left} = \frac{Rut_{Truck_left}}{Traffic_{total} \times Left_lane_{split} \times \%Truck_{left}} = WR_{Truck_right} \quad (5)$$

13 Where,

14 WR_{Truck_left} = Wear rate estimate due to trucks on the left lane (in/100,000 passes),

15 $Traffic_{total}$ = Total number of traffic during the period considered,

16 Rut_{Truck_left} = Rut depth due to truck on the left lane (inches),

17 $Left_lane_{split}$ = Percentage of traffic moving on the left lane, and

18 $\%Truck_{left}$ = Percentage of trucks moving on the left lane.

19
20 The rut depth in the right lane as a result of trucks is calculated using the wear rate from
21 trucks in the right lane as shown in Equation 6. Thus, the rut depth due to passenger vehicle is
22 achieved by subtracting rut depth in the right lane as a result of trucks from the total rut depth in
23 right lane.

$$25 \quad Rut_{Truck_right} = WR_{Truck_right} \times Traffic_{total} \times Right_lane_{split} \times \%Truck_{right} \quad (6)$$

$$26 \quad Rut_{PV_right} = Rut_{right} - Rut_{Truck_right} \quad (7)$$

27 Where,

28 Rut_{Truck_right} = Rut depth due to truck on the right lane (inches),

29 $Right_lane_{split}$ = Percentage of traffic moving on the right lane,

30 $\%Truck_{right}$ = Percentage of trucks moving on the right lane, and

31 Rut_{PV_right} = Rut depth due to studded passenger vehicle on the right lane (inches).

32
33 Finally, wear rate due to passenger vehicle is estimated using Equation 8. Since the
34 percentage of trucks in the right lane is significant compared to the left lane, the wear rate due to
35 passenger vehicles in right lane would be more feasible than the rate in the left lane as the number
36 of passenger car generally much higher than that of left lane. Therefore, wear rate due to passenger
37 vehicle in right lane is considered as the ultimate wear rate due to studded passenger vehicle for
38 freeways.

$$39 \quad WR_{PV_right} = \frac{Rut_{PV_right}}{Traffic_{7.5month} \times Right_lane_{split} \times \%Studs \times \%PV_{right}} \quad (8)$$

40 Where,

1 WR_{PV_right} = Wear rate estimate due to studded passenger vehicle on the right lane (in/100,000
 2 passes), and $\%PV_{right}$ = Percentage of passenger vehicles moving on the right lane.

3

4 **CASE STUDY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

5 The methodology was applied on several samples from Alaska roadway network including
 6 freeways, arterial, and collectors as a case study. The sample size and total mileage details
 7 considered for the analysis are shown in Table 1.

8

9 **Table 1. Samples and length of miles selected**

Classification	CDS Route #	Route Name	Total Miles
Freeways	135000	Glenn Highway	9.760
	130000	Seward Highway	6.000
	134300	Minnesota Drive	3.830
Arterials	133899	Tudor Road	5.728
	134750	Northern Lights Boulevard	8.160
	133700	Dimond Boulevard	4.416
	134130	Dowling Road	2.427
	133800	Intl. Airport Road	3.714
	133500	O'Malley Road	3.888
Collectors	133100	DeArmoun Road	3.735
	135225	Eagle River Road	6.486
	133710	Rabbit Creek Road	4.634
	133763	88th Ave Anchorage	0.852
	133743	100th Ave Anchorage	1.533
	134133	Brayton Drive	1.320
	133723	Hillside Drive	2.750
	133739	Lore Road	0.721
	134449	Post Road	1.640
	133755	Sand Lake Road	1.492

10

11 *Parking lot and household survey results*

12 A total of 1226 vehicles were surveyed. A majority of the surveyed vehicles were SUVs (45%),
 13 followed by passenger cars (32%), then trucks (19%), and then vans (4%). Overall, 61% of the
 14 vehicles as shown in Figure 2, were non-studded while 35% had studded tires. The percentage of
 15 vehicles with studded tires, differentiated by location, are shown in Figure 3. The figure indicates
 16 that the range of results between two visits are not significantly different, except that of Providence
 17 Hospital, DOT, and Walmart. The state owned vehicles at the DOT&PF Aviation Building might
 18 have biased the results because most state vehicles have studded tires. Further discussion is
 19 provided in the next section.

20

1
2 **Figure 2. Tire type of the surveyed vehicle**

4
5 **Figure 3. Studded tire use in different parking lots**

6
7 On the first visit of the parking lot survey, the average studded tire use was 34% with a standard deviation of 4%, whereas the average was 36% with a standard deviation of 6% for the second visit. Overall, the average studded tire use was 35% with a standard deviation of 5%. On the other hand, the household survey responses showed an average studded tire use of 48.6% per the sample population. A notable result from this survey is that 63.0% of the sample is considering switching from studded tires to new technology in winter tires, a trend that might decrease the percentage of studded tire traffic in the future. Also, 37.0% of the sample is not considering studless winter tires because of safety concerns (54.6%) and cost concerns (14.6%). The other reasons behind not considering studless tires are associated with public lack of awareness of non-studded winter tires; many drivers have no knowledge of current technology in winter tires.

17
18 Some households responded that they are aware of the performance of non-studded winter tires, but consider studded tires essential for winter driving, especially in hilly or mountainous areas to improve overall driving performance and safety, neglecting the fact that studs can cause rapid deterioration of pavement, which in itself will lead to other safety hazards. The majority of responses came from people 31–40 years of age (223 responses), 51–60 years of age (213 responses), and 21–30 years of age (201 responses). The fewest responses came from people 18–20 years of age (71 responses). Of the responses, 731 households own a first vehicle, and 455 of the vehicles are all-wheel drive and 372 have studded tires on all wheels. Also, 585 households own a second vehicle, and 386 of the vehicles are all-wheel drive and 242 have studded tires on

1 all wheels. Based on the respondents' experience with using new technology in winter tires, 62.6%
2 are not considering switching back to studs. Most respondents do not realize that studless winter
3 tires, in fact, provide traction and safety performance that is comparable to studded tires.
4

5 Results of the household online survey and parking survey reported differences in the
6 percentage of studded tire use. The online survey covered all regions of Alaska and the parking
7 survey covered only the Anchorage area. Previous studies on studded tire use conducted multiple
8 surveys, including parking lot surveys. The Oregon study on which the methodology was based
9 on compared the findings from a telephone survey and parking lot surveys. The studded tire usage
10 from the parking lot and telephone surveys for Region 5 of Oregon State was inconsistent, with
11 about a 20% difference, though results for other regions were reasonably consistent. Finally, the
12 study reported the overall studded tire usage from telephone surveys, which is the lower of the two
13 values.
14

15 *Wear rate results*

16 The freeway samples showed significant wear rates as a result of studded tires on the right lane,
17 higher than the wear caused by wheel loads. Figures 4, and figure 5 show a sample distribution
18 of rut depth measurements and wear rates on Glenn Highway only as an example due to space
19 limit.
20

21 **Figure 4. Glenn Highway Rut Depth**

22 **Figure 5. Glenn Highway wear rates**

1 Results from the freeway segments showed significantly higher average wear rates due to
 2 studded passenger vehicles—wear rates that reach 0.0116 in./100,000 studded vehicles compared
 3 with average rut rates on the right lane due to heavy wheel loads that reach 0.0049 in./100,000
 4 trucks. These results show evidence to support the claim that studded tires contribute to pavement
 5 deterioration more than heavy wheel loads.
 6

7 In the case of arterial and collector roads, it was hard to differentiate between rutting caused
 8 by wheel loads and rutting caused by studded tire traffic by using the methodology used on the
 9 freeway segments. A comparable methodology was applied over arterial and collector roads by
 10 assuming the same truck rut rates from freeways. An average truck rut rate of 0.0049 in./100,000
 11 trucks was assumed for arterial samples. Then, rut measurements due to percentage of truck traffic
 12 were calculated for each arterial segment. Rut measurements as a result of passenger vehicles were
 13 estimated by subtracting the rutting caused by truck traffic from the total rut depth. Finally, wear
 14 rates due to passenger vehicles were generated for each arterial segment. Results showed a
 15 significant lower average wear rate due to studded passenger vehicles on arterial roads, reaching
 16 0.0062 in./100,000 studded vehicles, compared with an average wear rate of 0.0116 in./100,000
 17 on freeway segments. Moreover, results showed a significantly lower average wear rate due to
 18 studded passenger vehicles on collector roads, reaching 0.0045 in./100,000 studded vehicles.
 19

20 **Cost estimates**

21 The cost estimate is divided into three sub-sections, one for each type of cost analysis that was
 22 employed. These estimates include pavement resurfacing and rehabilitation costs, pavement
 23 damage costs due to studded tires, and costs due to reduction of pavement life as a result of studded
 24 tires. Cost estimates were generated using wear rates and studded tire traffic data for the selected
 25 freeway segments in the case study. All cost estimates were expressed in terms of resurfacing and
 26 rehabilitation costs.
 27

28 *Resurfacing and rehabilitation cost estimates*

29 Several asphalt mix designs with different structural sections were considered to calculate the unit
 30 cost per square foot for resurfacing and rehabilitation. Data for these structural sections and total
 31 price per ton are shown in Table 2. The repair costs were limited to a rehabilitation strategy of the
 32 structural section thickness (mill/fill).
 33

34 **Table 2. Types of structural sections and unit price**

#	Structural Section	Unit price (\$/ton)
1	2" Stone Mastic Asphalt	65.00
2	2" & 4" Asphalt Concrete Type IA	135.00
3	2" HMA Type R	120.02
4	2" HMA Type V	95.00
5	1 .75" & 2" HMA Type R	105.54
6	2" HMA Type IIA*	84.45
7	2" HMA Type IIA*	65.85

1 A list of 20 actual projects was developed as shown in Table 3. Data from these projects
 2 were extracted from real as-built drawings to reflect the actual quantities used during construction.

3
 4 First, a realistic cost estimate was determined per pavement square foot of construction,
 5 which includes overall resurfacing costs (milling, striping, traffic maintenance and control). Then
 6 cost of total pavement damage was estimated for the rutting damage on the highways, including
 7 rutting damage that reaches the rut threshold limit. Based on feedback from Alaska DOT&PF, a
 8 0.5 in. rut threshold limit was taken into consideration to determine the cost of pavement
 9 resurfacing and rehabilitation. However, the exact weighted average for the rut threshold was
 10 estimated from the highway samples, including freeways and arterial and collector roads, to
 11 capture a range of costs and to provide future prediction cost estimates for Alaska DOT&PF.

12
 13 Finally, the pavement resurfacing cost was calculated for the 20 projects to establish a
 14 realistic estimated cost of construction/rehabilitation. Table 3 shows the calculated cost per square
 15 foot for each project.

16
 17 **Table 3. Pavement resurfacing cost per square foot**

Project Name	Total Cost (\$)	Cost/SF (\$)	Cost/Yr. (\$)
Northern Lights & Benson Resurfacing	2,392,208	1.70	341,744
Tudor Road Pavement Rehabilitation	5,928,633	3.08	846,948
Seward Highway MP 115–124 Resurfacing	6,516,993	2.86	930,999
C Street (52512)	1,068,535	15.83	152,648
Minnesota Drive Resurfacing	3,978,760	2.92	568,394
Glenn Highway	10,274,557	2.08	1,467,794
Muldoon Road Resurfacing	3,058,863	3.55	436,980
Sterling Highway Resurfacing	1,645,616	1.27	235,088
Minnesota Drive Resurfacing	3,679,828	4.17	525,690
Jewel Lake Road Resurfacing	1,635,944	3.64	233,706
Glenn Highway MP 34–42	1,617,275	1.93	231,039
Sterling Highway Resurfacing	2,779,942	3.11	397,135
Eagle River Loop Road Resurfacing	2,063,762	2.46	294,823
Dimond Boulevard Resurfacing	5,918,240	3.41	845,463
Glenn Highway Intersection Resurfacing	2,425,790	3.37	346,541
Dimond Resurfacing	3,856,123	2.85	550,875
Glenn Highway Resurfacing	7,728,503	2.04	1,104,072
Anchorage Resurfacing, Boniface Parkway	1,197,920	1.73	171,131
Anchorage Resurfacing, C Street	759,774	2.26	108,539
Anchorage Resurfacing, Lake Otis Parkway	853,825	2.07	121,975

18
 19 *Pavement Damage Cost Estimates Due to Studded Tires*

20 The best method of evaluating pavement damage as a result of studded tire traffic is to define the
 21 studded tire damage per vehicle miles traveled (VMT), and future damage predictions can be
 22 estimated and applied to any facility with a given VMT. Alaska DOT&PF provides VMT data that
 23 are published every year in the annual Traffic Volume Reports. First, the estimated studded tire

1 wear rate was multiplied by total VMT, as shown in Equation 9; the resulting number is equivalent
 2 to total studded tire rut depth. Since pavement resurfacing in Alaska is assumed to take place when
 3 rut depth reaches a threshold of 0.5 in., Equation 10 shows that the resulting rut depth value was
 4 divided by 0.5 to get the equivalent number of lane miles at that threshold. Finally, the total lane
 5 miles at threshold were multiplied by the average cost of resurfacing for each freeway, as shown
 6 in Equation 11.

$$7 \text{ Rut}_{\text{Lane-mile}} = \text{VMT}_{\text{studded_tires}} * \text{WR}_{\text{PV}} \quad (9)$$

8 Where,

9 $\text{Rut}_{\text{Lane-mile}}$ = total studded tire rut depth

10 WR_{PV} = Wear rate due to passenger vehicle

11 $\text{VMT}_{\text{studded_tires}}$ = Total Vehicle Miles Travelled * % of studded traffic

$$13 \text{ Rut}_{\text{Lane-mile @ threshold}} = \frac{\text{Rut}_{\text{Lane-mile}}}{0.5"} \quad (10)$$

14 Where,

15 $\text{Rut}_{\text{Lane-mile @ threshold}}$ = equivalent number of lane miles at 0.5" threshold

$$17 \text{ Total Cost} = \text{Rut}_{\text{Lane-mile @ threshold}} * \text{Cost}_{\text{Lane-mile}} \quad (11)$$

18
 19 The total number of lane miles is equivalent to the total rut depth reaching the threshold of 0.5 in.
 20 The resurfacing cost per square foot that was mentioned in Table 3 multiplied by 63,360 ft² to
 21 convert 1 ft² to get the total cost per one lane-mile (1 ft * 12 ft) for the freeway samples shown in
 22 Table 4.

23
 24 **Table 4. Pavement damage cost as a result of studded tires**

Sample	DVMT	Growth Rate	No. of Years	Sample VMT	Wear Rate	Total Rut (in.)	Total Rut Threshold	Cost \$/Lane-Mile
Glenn Highway	657394	1.50%	8	5262968	0.0122	0.6421	1.2840	\$169,238
Seward Highway	318842	0.50%	8	2551003	0.0108	0.2755	0.5510	\$99,846
Minnesota Drive	265424	0.50%	8	1867258	0.0118	0.2203	0.4406	\$81,516

25
 26 *Cost estimates due to reduction in pavement life*

27 Using the studded tire wear rates, for any highway segment with a given average studded tire daily
 28 traffic per lane, the level of studded tire traffic will equate to a certain value of damage per year.
 29 Alaska DOT&PF allows up to 0.5 in. of pavement wear before any scheduled rehabilitation.
 30 Dividing the rut threshold by the wear rate, as shown in Equation 12, a result of studded tires will
 31 equate to a number of years of expected pavement life. The difference between pavement design
 32 life and the expected life is equal to the total loss or cost due to studded tires.

$$1 \quad \text{Pavement}_{\text{life_expected}} = \frac{\text{Rut}_{\text{threshold}}}{\text{Annual}_{\text{studs_wear}}} \quad (12)$$

$$2$$

$$3 \quad \text{Pavement lifetime Loss} = \text{Pavement life}_{\text{Design}} - \text{Pavement life}_{\text{Expected}} \quad (13)$$

$$4$$

5 For example, for the Glenn Highway, which is a freeway selected in the case study, with
 6 an AADT of 10,000 vehicles per lane and 35% of vehicles having studded tires, there are 3,500
 7 vehicles with studded tires using that road per day. From September 15 to May 1, or for 227 days,
 8 there are 794,500 vehicles with studded tires per year on that segment of the highway, or 794,500
 9 studded passes per year. Using the wear rate of 0.0116 in. per 100,000 studded tire passes, this
 10 level of traffic equates to 0.0922 in. of studded tire wear per year. For a rut threshold of 0.5 in.,
 11 this roadway segment would need to be rehabilitated after 5.42 years. The normal pavement
 12 resurfacing cycle based on different threshold rut value of typical freeways in Anchorage ranges
 13 from 7 to 9 years with average of 8 years. Since the pavement design life in Anchorage is 15 years
 14 (McHattie, 2004) therefore, the effect of studded tires reduces the asphalt surface life by 6 to 8
 15 years with average of 7 years, which is a 46.67% loss of pavement life. With a given asphalt paving
 16 budget for Alaska statewide and with the percentage in reduction of pavement life, the total asphalt
 17 cost due to studded tires can be estimated as a monetary value.

18

19 **CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS**

20 In order to quantify the degree of pavement damage caused by studded tire use in Alaska,
 21 rut measurements and traffic data were collected from a sample of the state’s freeways and arterial
 22 and collector roads. Data were classified per directional split, lane split, and vehicle classifications
 23 including passenger vehicles and heavy trucks. A parking lot surveys and an online household
 24 surveys were employed to determine an approximate value of studded tire use. A total of 1226
 25 vehicles were surveyed in the parking lots throughout the Anchorage area where studded tire use
 26 was found to be 35%. More than 800 households, altogether owning 1531 vehicles, responded to
 27 the household online survey.

28

29 Data were analyzed and tabulated to differentiate between rutting caused by passenger
 30 vehicles using studded tires and rutting caused by trucks with heavy wheel axial loads. Results
 31 from the freeway segments show significantly higher average wear rates due to studded passenger
 32 vehicles—0.0116 in. per 100,000 studded vehicles—compared with average rut rates due to heavy
 33 wheel loads on the right lane—0.0049 in. per 100,000 trucks. Results also show significantly lower
 34 average wear rates due to studded passenger vehicles on arterial and collector roads, reaching
 35 0.0062 in. and 0.0045 in. per 100,000 studded vehicles, respectively. The pavement costs of
 36 resurfacing were calculated from as-builts of 20 similar historical projects. The average cost of
 37 pavement resurfacing ranged from \$2.06–\$3.24 per square foot, based on the pavement structural
 38 section. Estimates show that studded tire use reduced asphalt surface life on the selected freeway
 39 sample by about 7 years, which is about 47% loss in pavement life based on the initial design life
 40 of 15 years.

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